

**glycan
trigger**

D2.2 – Mechanistic effects of mucosa glycoprofile alteration on gut microbiota in mice associated with development of inflammation

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AUC	Area under the curve
CD	Crohn's Disease
DAI	Disease Activity Index
DSS	Dextran sulfate sodium
GlcNAc	N-Acetylglucosamine
IBD	Inflammatory Bowel Disease
IL	Interleukin
TNF	Tumour necrosis factor
UC	Ulcerative Colitis

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut. Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.2, titled “**Mechanistic effects of mucosa glycoprofile alteration on gut microbiota in mice associated with development of inflammation**”, investigates how host glycosylation, specifically the loss of complex branched N-glycans, drives the transition from health to intestinal inflammation in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Using glycoengineered Mgat5 knockout and conditional knockout mouse models, the study demonstrates that changes in mucosa glycosylation reshape gut microbial communities, as shown by 16S and ITS2 rRNA sequencing, which revealed distinct alpha and beta diversity profiles in both bacterial and fungal populations. Co-housing experiments further confirmed that microbiota transfer can modulate disease severity, highlighting glycan-mediated host-microbiota interactions as key regulators of gut homeostasis and potential targets for therapeutic intervention.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD) is a complex inflammatory condition that poses a significant global health burden.[1] It encompasses Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC), both of which remain challenging to manage clinically. Although the precise aetiology of IBD remains unclear, it is strongly associated with disruptions in the delicate interplay between the gut microbiota and immune recognition, often compounded by genetic predisposition. [2-4] Central to intestinal health is the epithelial barrier, which limits excessive interaction between microbial communities and the immune system.[5] Maintaining homeostasis requires a balanced relationship among microbiota, immune responses, and barrier integrity. When this equilibrium is disturbed, functional impairments arise, ultimately leading to intestinal inflammation.[6]

One key factor influencing intestinal equilibrium is host glycosylation, which has been widely reported as impaired in several diseases, including IBD. Glycosylation particularly affects T cell function and modulates immune responses in the gut.[7,8] Conversely, the precise impact of glycans on intestinal microorganisms remains underexplored. It is known that glycans can serve as a carbon source for gut microbes.[9-11] Indeed, previous studies have shown that synthetic glycans can directly modulate the gut microbiome, with dietary administration reducing gut pathogenesis in mice in therapeutic settings. [12]

However, it remains unclear whether host glycosylation can directly influence the composition of the intestinal microbiota associated with the transition from health to disease. Clarifying this relationship is essential for designing novel glycan-based strategies that target the intestinal microbiome to prevent gut inflammation and promote a healthy gut.

In this project, we will explore whether host glycosylation shapes the gut microbiota composition and how this can act as a hallmark of health-to-disease transition in IBD.

Chapter 2

Methods

2. Methods

2.1 Animals

C57BL/6 wild-type (*Mgat5*^{WT}) and *Mgat5*-deficient mice (*Mgat5*^{-/-}), as well as conditional knockout mice lacking complex N-glycans specifically in the gut mucosa, were bred and maintained in accredited animal facilities at the Institute for Research and Innovation in Health (i3S). Mice were housed in groups of 5-10, in HEPA filter-bearing cages, under 12-hour light/dark cycles. Autoclaved chow and water were provided *ad libitum*. Females between 9 and 14 weeks were used. Experiments were conducted with the approval of the Animal Ethics Committee and the Animal Welfare Body of the i3S. The protocols are in agreement with in-house standards and rules for animal experimentation, comply with national legislation and are integrated within a project, which is licensed by the Portuguese competent authority – DGAV (license number 009268/2022-06-02).

2.2 DSS-induced colitis

Mice with 9 to 11 weeks of age were given dextran sulfate sodium (DSS; 2% (w/v), molecular weight approximately 36,000–50,000 Da; MP Biomedicals) in the drinking water *ad libitum* for 7 days. Clinical signs of colitis, such as weight loss, stool consistency, and presence of blood were monitored daily and measured by the disease activity index (DAI). Mice were euthanized at the end of each experiment, or earlier if the symptoms of clinical disease reached one of these endpoints: more than 20% weight loss, diarrhoea, or gross bleeding.

2.3 Co-housing experiments

Four-week-old *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice were weaned and moved to the same cage, in order to share the same environment. Mice were housed in the same cage at a maximum amount of 10 mice per cage. Co-housing was performed for 5 weeks. Stool samples were collected before and after co-housing for both *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice.

2.4 16S rRNA sequencing, bioinformatic and statistical analysis of gut microbiota composition

Stools were collected before DSS treatment from mice, single-housed and co-housed, as well as before and after N-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) supplementation, and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen. [13] Microbiota composition was determined by 16S rRNA gene sequencing and analysed as previously described. [14] Sequencing was performed on an Illumina MiSeq platform (Illumina) at GenoScreen with

a 250-bp paired-end sequencing protocol. Raw paired-end reads were subjected to the following process: (1) quality filtering using the PRINSEQ-lite PERL script [15] by truncating the bases from the 3' end that did not exhibit a quality & less than 30 based on the Phred algorithm; (2) paired-end read assembly using FLASH (fast length adjustment of short reads to improve genome assemblies) with a minimum overlap of 30 bases and a 97% overlap identity; and (3) searching and removing both forward and reverse primer sequences using CutAdapt, with no mismatches allowed in the primers sequences. Assembled sequences without forward and reverse primers were removed.

Joined sequences were imported into the ampli con version of Qiime2 (version 2023.9). [16] Sequence inference was performed using Deblur. [17] Taxonomy was assigned using the SILVA database (v138.1). [18] Functional inference was performed using Picrust2 (v2.4.1). [19] All downstream analysis was performed in R and RStudio. The phyloseq package (v1.40.0) was used to handle and analyse microbiome data. [20] The vegan package (v2.6.2) was used to perform diversity analyses. Samples were rarefied to an even depth of the sample with the lowest counts prior to performing diversity analyses. Alpha diversity was calculated using the Chao1 and Shannon indices and beta diversity was calculated using the unweighted unifracs distance. [21] Pairwise differential abundance testing was performed between single-housed wild type vs single-housed *Mgat5*^{-/-}, as well as *Mgat5*^{-/-} single-housed vs co-housed animals with taxa agglomerated at the genus level and rarefied, as recently suggested, [22] using MaAsLin 2, [23] with the variable of interest a fixed-effect and the experiment as a random effect. “TSS” normalization and “LOG” transformation was used with prevalence filtering at 0.1. A q-value of 0.2 was applied to filter taxa. A similar analysis was performed using the unstratified pathway output of Picrust2 (*Mgat5*^{-/-} single-housed vs co-housed animals), without prior rarefaction and using a q-value of 0.05 and prevalence filtering of pathways in at least 50% of samples. For correlation of disease activity and differentially abundant taxa between *Mgat5*^{-/-} single-housed vs co-housed animals, the area-under-the-curve (calculated using the AUC function in the DescTools package (v0.99.54) with the “trapezoid” method) was calculated between day 0 and day 10 (with day 7 removed as some measurements were missing). Taxa were proportion-normalized, and the spearman correlation coefficient was used. Samples with a correlation p-value of <0.05 were manually plotted with the ‘stat_smooth’ function in ggplot2 using a “gam” method. All plotting was performed using ggplot2 (v3.4.1) and ggpubr (v0.4.0). Statistical tests of pairwise comparisons between independent groups were performed using the Wilcoxon rank sum test.

2.5 Cytokine quantification

For the colon explants, cytokine concentrations were analyzed by flow cytometry using cytometric bead arrays: the LEGENDplex™ MU Th Cytokine Panel (13-plex) (Biolegend), according to the manufacturer's instructions. Samples were measured on the BD Accuri C6 instrument (BD Biosciences, US) using a specific template provided by BD Biosciences.

Chapter 3

Results

3. Results

3.1 Changes in mucosa branched *N*-glycosylation promote gut dysbiosis associated with intestinal inflammation

Our previous evidence showed that the deficiency in the expression of complex branched *N*-glycans in *Mgat5* knockout mice (*Mgat5*^{-/-}) resulted in an early onset colitis in DSS-induced model, with mice developing severe forms of intestinal inflammation (Figure 1A). However, whether this deficiency on mucosa glycome may impact microbiota composition associated with colitis susceptibility remains unknown. We evaluated how the mucosa glycan switch imposed by the deficiency complex branched *N*-glycans and overexposure of mannose-enriched glycans affects the gut microbiota composition, by performing 16S (bacterial) and ITS2 (fungal) rRNA sequencing of luminal (fecal) content from distal small intestine, cecum and colon of *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice and *Mgat5*^{WT} mice in steady state (Figure 1B-C).

The results showed that mice lacking complex branched *N*-glycans display a clear dysbiotic microbiota composition at steady state when compared with *Mgat5*^{WT} mice. By analysing alpha (the variety of species within a sample, such as richness and diversity) and beta (differences in species composition between samples) diversities, we found that *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice have shown decreased bacterial alpha diversity, concomitant with a distinct beta diversity profile, in agreement with a dysbiotic profile (Figure 1B-C). For ITS2 sequencing, although the clustered of the two groups being not so distinct, *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice also showed a decreased alpha diversity, suggesting that the deficiency in branched *N*-glycans shape fungus composition towards a dysbiotic phenotype.

This profile found at steady-state, i.e., in homeostatic conditions, is accompanied by pro-inflammatory environment in the gut milieu, as *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice show increased levels of TNF- α and IL-6 in the supernatants from the colonic mucosa, as well as decreased levels of anti-inflammatory IL-10 (Figure 2 and Deliverable 3.1 – *Identification of the mechanism by which mucosa glycosylation switch regulates ILC-dependent immune response at gut mucosa*). These findings, demonstrating that alterations in host mucosal glycosylation impact both intestinal microbiota composition and gut immune responses, have been previously published by our group (Rodrigues & Gaifem et al. [13]).

Figure 1. Reduction of branched N-glycans in mice promotes gut dysbiosis.

(A) Disease activity score (DAI) of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} upon DSS-induced colitis. **(B-C)** Microbiota composition characterization at steady-state (homeostasis) of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} by analysis of 16S (B) and ITS2 (C) rRNA

sequencing of luminal content from distal small intestine, cecum and colon. The microbiota profile is displayed by assessment of alpha and beta diversity. Data is represented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure 2. Cytokine concentrations in supernatants of colonic explants of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice at steady state.

Levels of TNF- α (A), IL-6 (B) and IL-10 (C) in the supernatants of colonic explants cultured for 24 hours. The concentrations are normalized to tissue weight. Each datapoint represents an individual animal. Data is represented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$; **** $p < 0.0001$ using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t-test or Mann–Whitney test.

Besides the *Mgat5*^{-/-} mouse model, we also explored the microbiota composition in a mouse model lacking complex N-glycans specifically in the gut mucosa (here designated conditional knockout, cKO). We know that these mice are also more susceptible to severe colitis, similarly as *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice (Figure 3A). Interestingly, cKO mice were found to harbour a more attenuated dysbiotic phenotype, and with distinct clusters in beta diversity only found in samples collected from the distal small intestine (Figure 3B). For ITS2, no significant alterations were found in this strain (*data not shown*).

Although the cytokine levels in the colonic mucosa of these mice, at steady-state, were below detection level – which require further analysis to dissect if there are any basal alterations, we observed that, upon DSS-colitis, cKO mice display a more pro-inflammatory environment in the gut, with increased levels of IL-6 (Figure 4A) and a tendency for increased levels of IL-17A and TNF- α (Figure 4B-C). This reinforces the pivotal role of host glycosylation in shaping the susceptibility to intestinal disease.

Figure 3. Mice deficient in complex branched N-glycans at the gut mucosa have increased susceptibility to colitis concomitant with alterations in gut microbiota composition.

(A) Disease activity score (DAI) of WT and cKO mice upon DSS-induced colitis. **(B)** Microbiota composition characterization at steady-state (homeostasis) of WT and cKO mice by analysis of 16S rRNA sequencing of luminal content from distal small intestine, cecum and colon. The microbiota profile is displayed by assessment of alpha and beta diversity. Data is represented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 4. Cytokine concentrations in supernatants of colonic explants of WT and cKO mice at upon DSS-induced colitis.

Levels of IL-6 (A), IL-17A (B) and TNF-α (C) in the supernatants of colonic explants cultured for 24 hours. The concentrations are normalized to tissue weight. Each datapoint represents an individual animal. Data is represented as mean ± SD. **p < 0.01 using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t-test.

3.2 Sharing of the intestinal microbiota between *Mgat5*^{-/-} and *Mgat5*^{WT} mice impacts colitis susceptibility

To date, our data indicate that mice lacking complex branched N-glycans display a clear dysbiotic microbiota composition at steady state when compared with glycompetent mice. Consequently, we decided to explore the specific differences between these two groups. We initiated this analysis with the *Mgat5* mouse model since it has demonstrated a more striking dysbiotic phenotype.

Mgat5^{-/-} mice displayed an imbalance in the composition of different phyla when compared to *Mgat5*^{WT} mice, with significantly decreased abundance of specific taxa belonging to Firmicutes phylum, such as *Blautia*, *NK4A214* group and *Lachnoclostridium* genera. In contrast, the increased abundance of bacterial species such as *Marvinbryantia*, *Ruminococcaceae*, *Clostridia*_UCG_014, *Anaeroplasma*, and *Lachnospiraceae*_FCS020_group were detected in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice. Additionally, *Muribaculaceae* family from Bacteroidota phylum, *Coriobacteriaceae*_UCG_002, *Eggerthellaceae* from *Actinobacteriota* phylum and *Paracoccus* genus belonging to Proteobacteria phylum, were also found increased in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) of the gut microbiota composition based on 16S rRNA sequencing in the fecal samples of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice.

Data shows the variation of microbial taxa of single-housed (SH) *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice at steady state. Colours represent the different microbiota according to the phylum level.

We then sought to explore the role of the dysbiotic microbiota imposed by changes in host glycoalyx, in defining susceptibility to intestinal inflammation. For this, *Mgat5*^{-/-} and *Mgat5*^{WT} mice were co-housed (in the same cage), aiming to promote the sharing of their microbiota in a glycoengineered-dependent environment. Upon co-housing, colitis was induced with DSS (Figure 6A). Interestingly, co-housed *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice (CH-*Mgat5*^{-/-}) developed a less severe disease, as indicated by lower DAI and area under the curve (AUC) when compared with single-housed *Mgat5*^{-/-} (SH-*Mgat5*^{-/-}) (Figures 6B-C). Remarkably, co-housed *Mgat5*^{WT} (CH-*Mgat5*^{WT}) exhibited a worse disease course (Figures 6B-C), which supports the relevance of host glycosylation in dictating the susceptibility to intestinal inflammation in a process mediated by microbiota alterations.

Gut microbiota composition analysis upon co-housing further revealed a clear gain in terms of increased abundance and diversity in CH-*Mgat5*^{-/-} comparing with SH-*Mgat5*^{-/-} (Figures 6D-E), which is in line with the milder disease symptoms. Indeed, upon co-housing, colitis-susceptible *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice exhibited a pronounced modulation of gut microbiota, mainly characterized by the enrichment of Firmicutes bacteria, the downregulation of Proteobacteria and Actinobacteriota phyla, as well as an enrichment in species belonging to the *Turicibacter* genus (Figures 6F-H).

These results demonstrate the clear impact of the intestinal microbiota profile induced by mucosa *N*-glycosylation alterations (modelled in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice), in defining susceptibility to intestinal inflammation, putting glycans at the frontiers of host-microbiota interactions.

Figure 6 Co-housing of *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice with *Mgat5*^{WT} mice impacts gut dysbiosis and colitis susceptibility.

(A) Schematic representation of co-housing experiment. *Mgat5*^{-/-} and *Mgat5*^{WT} mice (controls) were co-housed for 5 weeks. Then, colitis was induced by giving ad libitum 2% DSS, in the drinking-water, for 7 days followed by normal water for 5 additional days. (B) Disease activity score (DAI) of single-housed (SH) and co-housed (CH) *Mgat5*^{-/-} and

Mgat5^{WT} mice upon DSS-induced colitis. **(C)** The area-under-the-curve (AUC) of DAI between single-housed (SH) and co-housed (CH) *Mgat5^{-/-}* and *Mgat5^{WT}* mice upon DSS-induced colitis. **(D)** Richness and evenness of fecal microbiota composition from mice before and after co-housing analyzed by 16S rRNA sequencing. **(E)** Principal component analysis (PCoA) of gut microbiota composition generated on Jaccard based on 16S rRNA sequencing. **(F)** Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) of the gut microbiota composition based on 16S rRNA sequencing in the fecal samples of single-housed (SH) and co-housed (CH) *Mgat5^{-/-}* mice at steady state. **(G-H)** Phylum and genus level gut microbiota composition analysis based on 16S rRNA sequencing in the fecal samples of single-housed (SH) and co-housed (CH) *Mgat5^{-/-}* and *Mgat5^{WT}* mice. (B-H) n = 5–8 per group. Each datapoint represents an individual animal. Data is represented as mean ± SD. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ****p < 0.0001 using two-way ANOVA or Wilcoxon rank sum test.

Chapter 4

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Chapter 5

Final Remarks

5. Final Remarks

Our results revealed that host glycosylation is capable to modulate the intestinal microbiota composition and function. Particularly, we found that mice lacking complex branched N-glycans display an intestinal dysbiotic phenotype that is associated with increased inflammation and severe colitis. These results support the relevance of host-microbiota interactions for gut health. The specific microbiota players involved in intestinal inflammation are now being explored, which will open new perspectives to tackle health to disease transition through host mucosa glycosylation-microbiome interaction. Hence, this will contribute to pinpoint the cascade of events associated with health-to-inflammation transition, aiming to pinpoint glycans as novel therapeutic targets for IBD prevention.

